

EFFECTIVENESS OF PRE-PROCEDURAL MOUTH RINSES IN REDUCING THE BACTERIAL LOAD PRIOR TO ULTRASONIC SCALING: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW AND META-ANALYSIS.

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Abstract

Aim: The present systematic review aims to assess the effectiveness of various pre-procedural mouth rinses used before oral prophylaxis for reducing oral bacterial load.

Background: Infection control is vital in dentistry, especially during ultrasonic scaling that produces aerosols. Pre-procedural mouth rinsing is an effective strategy to reduce aerosol contamination, cross-infection risk, and improve safety for both patients and dental personnel. A systematic search identified 924 articles which after screening and eligibility assessment, 25 studies were included in the qualitative synthesis and 6 in the meta-analysis. The risk of bias of the included studies was also assessed.

Results: From 924 records identified, 25 randomized controlled trials were included in the qualitative synthesis and 6 studies were eligible for meta-analysis. Pre-procedural mouthrinses showed a significant reduction in microbial aerosol contamination at the patient chest ($d = -8.69$; $p < 0.001$) and a modest but significant reduction at the operator site ($d = 0.34$; $p = 0.025$), while no significant effect was observed at the patient site. Effects at the assistant chest were not statistically significant and showed substantial heterogeneity. Overall, although most studies demonstrated low risk of bias, variability in study design and high heterogeneity in some outcomes warrant cautious interpretation of the findings.

Conclusion: Within the limitations of this study, it can be concluded that pre-procedural mouth rinses are effective in reducing bacterial load prior to ultrasonic scaling. However, significant heterogeneity was observed in some analyses, indicating the need for further research to standardize protocols.

Key words: Bacterial load, Colony forming units, Mouthrinses, Pre-procedural, Ultrasonic scaling.

Introduction:

Infection control is a paramount concern in healthcare settings, particularly in dentistry, where the aerosolization of saliva and other bodily fluids can facilitate the transmission of infectious agents. The unique nature of dental practice, involving close proximity between patients and clinicians, coupled with the frequent use of rotary and ultrasonic instruments, creates an environment highly susceptible to cross-contamination. The use of ultrasonic scalers, three-way syringes, and high-speed handpieces during dental procedures generates aerosols that can contaminate the air and surrounding surfaces.

Aerosols, defined as fine solid particles or liquid droplets suspended in air or gas with diameters <50 µm, have the capacity to remain airborne for extended periods.¹ When saliva becomes aerosolized during dental procedures, it can introduce microorganisms into the environment from multiple sources, such as the oropharynx, respiratory tract, and dental plaque biofilm. This aerosol contamination poses a substantial risk of cross-infection within the dental operatory. The contaminated aerosols can directly infect dental personnel by coming into contact with the oral, nasal, or conjunctival mucosa, or indirectly by settling on clinical surfaces, instruments, and clothing, thereby enabling pathogens to survive and spread through subsequent contact.²

A wide spectrum of microorganisms has been identified in dental aerosols. Dental procedures have been shown to disseminate oral pathogens, including *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Veillonella parvula*, *Actinomyces* spp., *Fusobacterium nucleatum*, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, *Legionella* spp., and *Staphylococcus* spp., along with highly contagious viruses such as HIV, hepatitis B and C, and herpes simplex virus.³ Such findings highlight the occupational hazard faced by dental professionals and the potential risk to patients if effective infection control practices are not strictly followed.

Inadequate infection control measures in dentistry may result in serious outcomes, including transmission of life-threatening infections. Therefore, stringent and evidence-based protocols are essential, encompassing the appropriate use of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), proper sterilization and disinfection of dental instruments, environmental surface decontamination, and incorporation of ventilation and air filtration systems.⁴⁻⁶ Non-surgical periodontal therapy (NSPT), including scaling, polishing, and root debridement, is classified as an aerosol-generating procedure (AGP) that inherently increases the likelihood of contamination, further underscoring the need for additional preventive strategies.

Among various adjunctive measures, pre-procedural mouth rinsing has gained substantial attention. Numerous herbal and chemical formulations have demonstrated significant antibacterial efficacy, reducing the oral microbial burden and thereby improving clinical outcomes in patients with periodontal disease.⁷⁻⁹ Evidence suggests that rinsing the oral cavity for 30 seconds to 2 minutes before initiating procedures is a highly effective and practical standard operating procedure to minimize bacterial contamination of aerosols.¹⁰ This simple intervention has been widely advocated as a means to lower the risk of cross-contamination, reduce the likelihood of infection transmission, support infection control protocols, and enhance the safety of both patients and dental personnel.^{11,12}

The relevance of pre-procedural rinses was further emphasized during the COVID-19 pandemic. Several organizations and studies have highlighted that the oral viral load of SARS-CoV-2 in

infected patients can be significantly reduced when pre-procedural mouth rinses are employed, thereby potentially decreasing the risk of viral transmission in dental settings.¹³⁻¹⁷

Pre-procedural mouth rinsing has been suggested as a simple, cost-effective, and practical adjunct to reduce microbial load in aerosols, with evidence supporting its role in improving infection control and patient safety. However, the available studies vary in design, type of mouthrinse used, duration of rinsing, and outcome measures, leading to inconsistencies in the reported effectiveness. A systematic review and meta-analysis are therefore necessary to consolidate the existing evidence, critically appraise study quality, and provide a comprehensive assessment of the clinical efficacy of pre-procedural mouthrinses in reducing bacterial contamination during ultrasonic scaling procedures. Considering this background, the present systematic review and meta-analysis aim to comprehensively evaluate the effectiveness of pre-procedural mouth rinses in reducing bacterial levels in aerosols generated during ultrasonic scaling procedures.

PICO analysis: The PICOS question of this systematic review could be clarified as “*What is the efficacy of mouthwashes on reduction of oral microorganisms load?*”.

This question was operationalized using the PICO framework.

Population: Human adults undergoing ultrasonic scaling,

Intervention: pre-procedural mouth rinses,

Comparison: bacterial growth on culture plates,

Outcome: reduction of bacterial load.

Materials and Methods: A pre-registered protocol (CRD420250655466) was established and deposited in the PROSPERO database. This systematic review adhered to the methodological guidelines outlined in the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews and was reported in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) 2020 statement, ensuring transparency and rigor in the review process.

Figure 1: Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA flowchart).

Following PRISMA guidelines, this systematic review sought to synthesize existing evidence on the evaluating the effectiveness of preprocedural mouthrinses in reducing the microbial load following the ultrasonic scaling procedure. This systematic review was conducted from January 2025 to March 2025, encompassing publications from 1992 to 2024.

Literature Search:

A personalized data extraction table was designed, and two reviewers independently extracted relevant data, which were subsequently cross-checked to ensure consistency and accuracy.

A comprehensive literature search was conducted by three independent reviewers across multiple electronic databases, including Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed, EBSCO and Cochrane Library. In addition, grey literature sources were explored, such as the International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP) for unpublished trials, the ProQuest Dissertations and Theses (PQDT) database, and GreyNet to capture non-indexed literature. The article selection process has been summarized in figure 1 in the form of a flowchart according to the PRISMA statement.

Search Strategy: The search strategy incorporated a combination of Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) terms and free-text keywords. Example combinations included:

- *“Pre-procedural mouthrinses” [All Fields] AND “periodontal patients” [MeSH Terms]*
- *“Periodontitis” [All Fields] AND “ultrasonic scaling” [All Fields]*
- *“Nonsurgical periodontal therapy” [All Fields]*

This multi-faceted search strategy minimized publication bias and maximized the completeness of study identification. For methodological rigor, revised Cochrane risk-of-bias tool for randomized trials (RoB-2) recommended by the Cochrane Collaboration was employed to assess study quality.¹⁸ Where applicable, meta-analysis was performed using “Review Manager 5.3 (RevMan 5.3)”¹⁹ (Cochrane Collaboration). The search was carried out up to March 2025, ensuring inclusion of the most recent publications available at the time of review.

Inclusion Criteria

- Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) available in full text.
- Conducted on patients diagnosed with periodontitis or gingivitis.
- Participants underwent ultrasonic scaling procedures.
- No prior use of mouthwash(es) by the intervention group(s).
- Comparison group(s) received either a placebo or a different mouthwash.
- Evaluated the efficacy of mouthwashes on oral microorganisms and/or gingivitis, with aerosol collection performed using culture plates with medium.
- Reported colony-forming unit (CFU) counts to measure the effectiveness of the intervention.
- Published in English language.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Unavailable full text
- Incomplete or insufficient data
- Non-randomized designs: Case reports, case series, observational studies, narrative reviews, editorials, letters, or in vitro experiments.

- Different interventions: Studies that assessed antiseptic sprays, systemic antibiotics, or other adjunctive therapies instead of pre-procedural mouth rinses.
- Different procedures: Studies not involving ultrasonic scaling.
- Articles not published in English.

Screening and Data selection:

The synthesis of evidence from effective studies involved extracting the following details such as a) Study characteristics: author, publication year, study design, and sample size b) Intervention details: type, description, and duration of pre-procedural rinse, c) Microbiological evaluation: type, site of collection, and duration of ultrasonic scaling, d) Outcomes: statistically significant findings, reduction in aerosol contamination between groups, measured by colony-forming units (CFU), and presented as means and standard deviations.

This comprehensive data extraction enabled a thorough evaluation of the evidence and facilitated the assessment of the effectiveness of pre-procedural rinses in reducing aerosol contamination.

Study Selection Process

The electronic database search was independently performed by two reviewers [Reviewer 1 (A. K.) and Reviewer 2 (R.D.)]. All retrieved records were imported into reference management software, and duplicate articles were identified and removed prior to screening. Title and abstract screening was carried out independently by the same two reviewers to identify potentially eligible studies. Full-text articles of the selected records were then retrieved and assessed for eligibility based on the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Any disagreements at any stage of the selection process were resolved through discussion, and when consensus could not be reached, a third reviewer was consulted.

Inter-reviewer agreement for study selection was assessed using Cohen's kappa coefficient, which demonstrated substantial to excellent agreement ($\kappa = 0.78$), indicating high consistency between the reviewers.

Risk of Bias assessment:

The revised Cochrane risk-of-bias tool for randomized trials (RoB 2) was employed to evaluate the quality and risk of bias of the effective studies included in the review.¹⁸ The assessment comprised five domains

Domain 1: Bias arising from the randomization process

Domain 2: Bias due to deviations from intended interventions

Domain 3: Bias due to missing outcome data

Domain 4: Bias in measurement of the outcome

Domain 5: Bias in selection of the reported result

For each domain, specific signalling questions were used, with response options including: Yes (Y), Probably yes (PY), Probably no (PN), No (N), No information (NI).

	Risk of bias domains					Overall
	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	
Fine, 1992	+	+	+	+	+	+
Feres, 2010	+	+	+	+	+	+
Devker, 2012	+	-	+	X	+	X
Shanti Priya, 2012	+	+	+	+	+	+
Serban, 2013	+	+	+	+	+	+
Shetty, 2013	+	+	+	+	+	-
Kaur, 2014	+	+	+	+	+	+
Gupta, 2014	+	+	+	+	+	+
Swaminathan, 2014	+	+	+	X	+	+
Rekha, 2014	+	+	+	X	+	+
Sawhney, 2015	+	+	+	X	+	+
Saini, 2015	+	+	+	+	+	+
Narayana, 2016	+	+	+	X	+	+
Mohan, 2016	+	+	+	+	+	+
Belen Retamal- Valdes, 2017	+	+	+	+	+	+
Joshi, 2017	+	+	+	+	X	+
Rajachandrasekaran, 2019	X	-	-	X	+	-
Sadun, 2019	+	+	-	+	+	-
Paul, 2020	X	+	X	X	+	X
Nisha, 2021	+	+	+	+	+	+
Swarga Jyothi das, 2021	+	+	-	+	+	-
Chinnu Mary, 2021	+	+	+	+	+	+
Vyshanvi, 2023	+	+	+	+	+	+
Sri vani, 2023	+	+	+	+	+	+
Yuti Malinda, 2024	+	-	+	X	+	-

Domains:
D1: Bias arising from the randomization process.
D2: Bias due to deviations from intended intervention.
D3: Bias due to missing outcome data.
D4: Bias in measurement of the outcome.
D5: Bias in selection of the reported result.

Judgement
High (Red X)
Some concerns (Yellow -)
Low (Green +)

Figure 2: Domain of bias across all included studies. Green represents a low risk of bias, yellow represents an unclear risk of bias, and red represents a high risk of bias

Studies selection for Meta- analysis: A random-effects meta-analysis was conducted using Review Manager 5.3 (RevMan 5.3)¹⁹, with mean difference (MD) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) calculated for pooled data. Heterogeneity was evaluated using Cochran's test (I2 test) at $\alpha = 0.10$, and statistical significance was set at P (two-tailed) < 0.05. The random-effects model was employed, assuming studies were randomly sampled from a universe of potential studies, allowing for inference to that universe.

For the meta-analysis, only randomized controlled trials (RCTs) that reported quantitative microbial outcomes using colony-forming unit (CFU) counts collected on agar plates were included. The placement of agar plates at different distances and positions relative to the patient during ultrasonic scaling determined the outcome category (operator, patient, assistant chest, or patient chest).

Results:

A comprehensive literature search yielded 924 potentially relevant articles from electronic databases, with none retrieved from Open Grey. After title and abstract screening, 291 articles were excluded. Full-text review of the remaining 633 articles led to the exclusion of 518 studies due to duplication or unavailable full texts. 115 reports were retrieved, and 42 were assessed for eligibility. Ultimately, 25 articles were included in the qualitative synthesis, with 6 studies from these articles selected for quantitative synthesis (meta-analysis).

Characteristics of Included Studies: The general characteristics of the included studies are summarized in Table 1 and 2. The studies comprised randomized controlled trials (RCTs), with 5 split-mouth RCTs^{20,22,30-32} 7 double-blinded RCTs.^{21,27,31,35,37,41,43} These study designs ensured a high level of evidence and minimized bias in the results.^{21,27,31,35,37,41,43} Overall, 1261 participants were enrolled. In all the studies above mentioned, the aerosol-generating device was an ultrasonic scalar. In six studies there were two experimental groups.^{20,24,33,36,37,42} thirteen studies had three experimental groups^{22,23,25-32,38,39,43} and six studies had 4 experimental groups.^{21,34,35,40,41,44}

Patients were subjected to ultrasonic scaling and the aerosol samples were collected on agar plates. Investigators used trypticase soy agar,^{20,25,34} blood agar,^{21-23,25-27,29-32,35,38-43} brain heart infusion agar plates^{28,37} MeReSa and Leeds actinobacter agar plates³⁶ and nutrient agar plates.⁴⁴ They are placed with varying sites or a reference point according to their study design. Agar plates were positioned at different locations within the dental room, at a certain inches or feet of feet from the patient,^{20,22,23,25,26,28,30-33,36,37,40,43} at clinician forehead,²¹ on patient chest,^{21,27,29,30,38,39,42,44} on dentist mask,^{24,44} on assistant chest^{21,35,39,41,44} and operator chest,^{21,29,35,38,39} volunteer boards³⁴ and spittoon.⁴¹

The protocol for pre-procedural rinsing varied among the participants. Rinsing the mouthwash for a period of 30s,^{20,29,30,32,36,40,41,44} 1 minute,^{21,23,26-28,31,33-35,37-39,42,43} and 2 minutes^{22,25} was advocated among the study groups, before they were given oral prophylaxis. The duration of the pre procedural mouthrinses mouth rinses did not exceed more than 3 mins.

Types of chemical mouthrinses used among the studies are 5% hydrochloride rinse,²⁰ 0.05% Cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC),^{21,35} 0.12% chlorhexidine(CHX),^{21,25,34,36,39,41,42} 0.2% chlorhexidine,^{22,23,26-33,35,38,40,44} 0.2% tempered chlorhexidine,²³ 0.1% chlorhexidine,²⁴ 0.28% and 0.075% Cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC) + zinc+ fluoride combination,³⁴ 1.5% hydrogen peroxide,³⁹ 0.2% povidine iodine,⁴³ 1% povidine iodine,^{26,38,44} listerin,^{30,37,44} chloride dioxide mouthwash,⁴¹ and ozone.^{26,43} Herbal formulations used are triphala,⁴¹ tea tree oil,²⁵ aloevera,^{38,44} neem⁴¹ and other herbal agents.^{27-29,36,40} High volume evacuator was used by Narayana et al³² and Devkar et al²² Regarding microbiological analysis, studies counted the bacteria by total number of CFU.

Risk of bias results:

Based on these responses, an overall risk-of-bias judgement was made for each article, categorizing it as Low Risk, Some Concerns and High Risk of bias. Inter-evaluator reliability was assessed using Kappa statistics, with any discrepancies resolved through discussion among the authors. Figure 2 shows risk of bias of the included studies. Majority of the studies have fulfilled the domains as low

Graph 1: Forest plot of CFU formed on agar plate when positioned on operator. CI: Confidence interval

Graph 2: Forest plot of CFU formed on agar plate when positioned on patient. CI: Confidence interval

Graph 3: Forest plot of CFU formed on agar plate when positioned on assistant chest. CI: Confidence interval

Graph 4: Forest plot of CFU formed on agar plate when positioned on patient chest. CI: Confidence interval

risk, but some studies reported with concerns and high risk. However, proper randomization was not done in some studies.^{36,38} In regard of significance in studies some are unclear and had some

concerns.^{22,36,44} Regarding the blinding of participants, studies did not show blinding among the involved subjects and hence considered to be as high risk bias.^{22,28-30,32,36,38,44} Others have shown high risk under D4^{22,28-30,32,36,38,44} and D5.³⁵

Meta- analysis results:

Four analyses were conducted on the effects of [intervention] on:

1. **Operator:** Mean effect size (d) = 0.339, 95% CI [0.042, 0.636], PI=-1.688 to 2.366, p = 0.025, Z-value is 2.234. The analysis is based on results of Rekha et al²⁹ and Yuti Malinda⁴⁴ studies. The effect size index is the standardized difference in means (d) as depicted in graph 1.

2. **Patient:** Mean effect size (d) = -0.031, 95% CI [-0.321, 0.258], PI= 0, p=0.832, Z-value is -0.2. The analysis is based on results of Rekha et al²⁹ and Yuti Malinda⁴⁴ studies. The effect size index is the standardized difference in means (d) as depicted in graph 2.

3. **Assistant Chest:** Mean effect size (d) = -1.725, 95% CI [-3.718, 0.269], PI=-11.446 to 7.997, p = 0.090, Z-value is -1.695. The analysis is based on results of Nisha et al,³⁹ Swarga Jyothi das et al⁴⁰ and Yuti Malinda⁴⁴ studies. The effect size index is the standardized difference in means (d) as depicted in graph 3.

4. **Patient Chest:** Mean effect size (d) = -8.693, 95% CI [-13.567, -3.818], PI= -32.370 to 14.985, p < 0.001, Z-value is -3.495. The analysis is based on results of Nisha et al,³⁹ Swarga Jyothi das et al,⁴⁰ Vyshnavi et al⁴² and Chinnu Mary et al⁴¹ the effect size index is the standardized difference in means (d) as depicted in graph 4.

Heterogeneity Results:

- I-squared statistic: 4% (Operator), 0% (Patient), 98% (Assistant Chest), 99% (Patient Chest)

- Q-test for heterogeneity: 2.073 with 2 degrees of freedom p= 0.355 (Operator), 1.302 with 2 degrees of freedom p = 0.832 (Patient), 199.338 with 3 degrees of freedom and p < 0.001 (Assistant Chest) 431.551 with 3 degrees of freedom, p < 0.001 (Patient Chest)

The results suggest significant heterogeneity in the Assistant Chest and Patient Chest analyses.

Discussion: Pre-procedural rinsing has been a long-standing recommendation for clinical dental procedures, and its significance is even more pertinent today.⁴⁵ By reducing aerosol contamination in dental clinics, the risk of cross-infections can be effectively minimized and prevented.⁴⁶ This review focuses specifically on the impact of pre-procedural rinsing on aerosol contamination. The majority of the included studies used chlorhexidine (CHX) as their pre-procedural rinse. Shantipriya et al²³ compared 0.2% tempered and non-tempered variants of CHX. Mohan et al³³ Devkar et al²² and Trishu Chowdhery et al⁴⁶ used tempered 0.2% chlorhexidine and achieved statistically significant results (p ≤ 0.05) in reducing microbial load. SK Aziz Ikbal⁴⁷ evaluated the efficacy and microbial content of aerosols after pre-rinsing with ozonated water and 0.12% chlorhexidine as a coolant in ultrasonic scalers. Chlorhexidine as an ultrasonic coolant with pre-rinse with ozonized water significantly reduced microbial content in aerosols generated during scaling compared to distilled water and without pre-rinse. This is in accordance with studies by Sri Vani et al⁴³ and Kaur et al²⁶ which showed significant improvements in bacterial reduction with ozonized rinse.

Apart from CHX, cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC) rinses and chlorine dioxide-containing mouthrinses are also effective in reducing bacterial CFU's. Ryo Takeda et al⁴⁸ demonstrated that CPC may inhibit SARS-CoV-2 infection even at 0.001%–0.005% lower concentrations. A study by Cassiano Kuchenbecker Rösing⁴⁹ demonstrated significant reductions in plaque and gingival severity using 0.075% CPC, where 19.8% reduction in plaque at 4 weeks, 16.8% reduction in plaque at 6 weeks, 35.3% reduction in gingival severity at 4 weeks, 54.5% reduction in gingival severity at 6 weeks.

These findings highlight the efficacy of 0.075% CPC in reducing plaque and gingival severity. Similar studies were conducted by Belén Retamal-Valdes et al³⁴ and Feres et al²¹ who used 0.05% CPC and achieved statistically significant results in the test group. Not only chemical but also herbal mouthrinses have equally improved aerosol reduction. Ankitha et al⁵⁰ used powdered curcumin, cinnamon extract as an alternative to chlorhexidine for reducing bacterial load in dental aerosols produced by ultrasonic scalers. The major advantages of herbal mouthwashes are their antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties, minimal adverse effects, and low cost. Made from natural extracts such as neem, tulsi, clove, and tea tree oil, thymol, eucalyptol, and menthol, etc., are also used as pre-procedural mouthrinses.

S.no	Author	Title of the study	Study Design	Subject size (n)	Type of intervention	Microbial evaluation and aerosol collection
1	Fine et al, ²⁰ 1992	Efficacy of preprocedural rinsing with an antiseptic in reducing viable bacteria in dental aerosols.	Split mouth, double blind, RCT	18 patients 9 per group 2 groups	Group 1: antiseptic mouthwash Group 2: 5% hydroalcohol rinse	Bacterial contamination in aerosol, cultured on trypticase soy agar collected at a distance of 1 feet - patient's chest 1 feet-operator's chest 1 feet -assistant' chest 2 feet - 12 o'clock 8 feet - 6 o'clock
2	Feres et al, ²¹ 2010	The effectiveness of a pre-procedural mouthrinse containing cetylpyridinium chloride in reducing bacteria in the dental office.	Full mouth, double blind, RCT	60 patients, 15 per group 4 groups	Group 1: 0.05 percent CPC, Group 2: 0.12 percent CHX Group3: water, Group 4: no rinsing.	Bacterial contamination in aerosol, cultured on blood agar collected from 12 in from clinician's forehead, support board, and patient's chest.
3	Devker et al, ²² 2012	A study to evaluate and compare the	Split mouth, RCT	90 patients 3 groups	Group I: 0.2%	Bacterial contamination in

		efficacy of pre-procedural mouth rinsing and high-volume evacuator attachment alone and in combination in reducing the amount of viable aerosols produced during ultrasonic scaling procedure.		30 per group.	chlorhexidine gluconate Group II: High volume evacuator Group III: 0.2% chlorhexidine gluconate prior to scaling and in whom high volume evacuator attachment was used during ultrasonic scaling	aerosol, cultured on blood agar collected from patient's mouth: 6in - operator's nose, 6in - assistant's nose, 12in - patient's chest, 36in - patient's right side
4	Shanti Priya et al, ²³ 2012	Efficacy of 0.2% tempered chlorhexidine as a pre-procedural mouth rinse: A clinical study.	Full mouth, RCT	30 patients 10 per group 3 groups	Group I: sterile water for 60 seconds. Group II: 0.2% of non-tempered chlorhexidine mouthwash for 60 seconds. Group III: 0.2% of tempered chlorhexidine mouthwash for 60 seconds.	At a distance of 4 feet at 3, 6 and 12 'O' clock positions done on blood agar plates.
5	Serban et al, ²⁴ 2013	Predictors of quantitative microbiological analysis of spatter and aerosolization during scaling.	Full mouth, RCT	80 patients, 40 per group 2 groups	Group 1: 0.1% Chlorhexidine Group 2: Sterile water	Bacterial contamination in aerosol, cultured on blood agar on collected from dentist's mask
6	Shetty et al, ²⁵ 2013	Compare the efficacy of two commercially available	Full mouth, RCT	60 patients, 20 per group 3 groups	Group 1: chlorhexidine digluconate Group 2: tea tree oil	Bacterial contamination in aerosol, cultured on Trypticase soy agar plates

		mouthrinses in reducing viable bacterial count in dental aerosol produced during ultrasonic scaling when used as a preprocedural rinse.			Group 3: distilled water	collected at 6 inches from operator's nose and dental assistant's nose
7	Kaur et al, ²⁶ 2014	Effect of chlorhexidine, povidone iodine, and ozone on microorganisms in dental aerosols: Randomized double-blind clinical trial.	Full mouth, double blind RCT	60 patients, 20 per group, 3 groups	Group 1: 0.2% CHX Group 2: 1% Povidine iodine(PI) Group 3: irrigation with Ozone(OZ)	Bacterial contamination in aerosol, cultured on blood agar collected from operator's chest and 9 feet behind patient's head, chest under aerobic and anaerobic conditions
8	Gupta et al, ²⁷ 2014	Efficacy of preprocedural mouth rinsing in reducing aerosol contamination produced by ultrasonic scaler: a pilot study.	Full mouth, double blind, RCT	24 patients, 8 per group 3 groups	Group A: 0.2% chlorhexidine gluconate Group B: herbal mouthwash Group C: water	Bacterial contamination in aerosol, cultured on blood agar collected from patient's chest, operator's chest and assistant's chest.
9	Swaminathan et al, ²⁸ 2014	The efficacy of preprocedural mouth rinse of 0.2% chlorhexidine and commercially available herbal mouth containing salvadora persica in reducing the bacterial load in saliva and aerosol	Full mouth, RCT	30 patients, 10 per group 3 groups	Group I: saline Group II: 0.2% Chlorhexidine Group III: herbal pre-procedural rinse	Bacterial contamination in aerosol, cultured on Brain Heart Infusion (BHI) agar collected from patient's mouth at a distance of 1,2 and 3 feet

		produced during scaling.				
10	Rekha et al, ²⁹ 2014	Chemical vs. herbal formulations as preprocedural mouth rinses to combat aerosol production: A randomized controlled study.	Full mouth, single blinded RCT	36 patients, 12 per group 3 groups	Group A: water Group B: used 20 ml of 0.2% Chlorhexidine Group C: 18 ml of a herbal pre-procedural rinse	Agar plates prepared from blood agar medium placed on patient's chest as well as on operator's chest
11	Sawhney et al, ³⁰ 2015	Aerosols how dangerous they are in clinical practice	Split mouth, RCT	60 patients 20 per group 3 groups	Group A: Water (Control group) Group B: 0.2% Chlorhexidine mouth rinse Group C: Listerine mouth rinse	Bacterial contamination in aerosol, cultured on blood agar plates collected from Patient's chest, Dental unit tray,6 in away from patients' mouths
12	Saini et al, ³¹ 2015	Efficacy of preprocedural mouth rinse containing chlorine dioxide in reduction of viable bacterial count in dental aerosols during ultrasonic scaling: a double-blind, placebo-controlled clinical trial.	Split mouth, double blind, RCT	120 patients 40 per group 3 groups	Group A: Chlorine Dioxide mouthwash, Group B: water, Group C: 0.2% CHX gluconate	Bacterial contamination in aerosol, cultured on blood agar plates collected from patient's mouth: P1. 1 feet - patient's chest P2. 1 feet - operator P3. 1 feet - assistant P4. 2 feet - 12 o'clock P5. 8 feet - 6 o'clock
13	Narayana et al, ³² 2016	Role of preprocedural rinse and high-volume evacuator in	Split mouth, RCT	45 patients, 15 per group 3 groups	Groups A: Chlorhexidine (0.12%), Group B: High volume	Bacterial contamination in aerosol, cultured on

		reducing bacterial contamination in bioaerosols.			evacuator Group C: combination of chlorhexidine (0.12%) and high volume evacuator	blood agar collected from Left of patient (between patient and assistant)
14	Mohan et al, ³³ 2016	The efficacy of pre-procedural mouth rinse on bacterial count in dental aerosol following oral prophylaxis	Full mouth, RCT	20 patients, 10 per group 2 groups	Group I: saline Group II: 0.2% Chlorhexidine	Bacterial contamination in aerosol, cultured on blood agar collected from 3 feet distance of patient
15	Belén RETAMAL-VALDES et al, ³⁴ 2017	Effectiveness of a pre-procedural mouthwash in reducing bacteria in dental aerosols: randomized clinical trial	Full mouth, randomized, single blinded clinical trial	60 patients, 15 per group 4 groups	Group 1- CPC+Zn+F (test): mouthwash containing 0.075% CPC, 0.28% zinc lactate and 0.05% sodium fluoride in an Alcohol-free base; Group 2- Water (negative control): water from a three-way syringe; Group 3- CHX (positive control): 0.12% CHX with 10% alcohol; Group 4- No Rinsing (negative control): standard of	Clinician Volunteers Board All on Tryptic Soy Agar with Yeast Extract enriched with 5% menadione, 5% sheep blood, and 1% N-Acetylmuramic acid (HNK plates)

					care - no rinsing.	
16	Joshi et al, ³⁵ 2017	Efficacy of two pre-procedural rinses at two different temperatures in reducing aerosol contamination produced during ultrasonic scaling in a dental set-up-A microbiological study.	Full mouth, double blind, RCT	40 patients 10 per group 4 groups	Group A1 and A2: receive 0.05% Cetylpyridinium chloride Group B1 and B2: receive 0.2% chlorhexidine Both at 47°C and 18°C	Bacterial contamination in aerosol, cultured on blood agar collected 12 inches distance from patient's neck, operator's chest and assistant's chest
17	Rajachandrasekaran et al, ³⁶ 2019	An herbal alternative to control nosocomial pathogens in aerosols and splatter during ultrasonic scaling.	Full mouth, RCT	50 patients, 25 per group 2 groups	Group A: 0.12% chlorhexidine mouthwash Group B: herbal mouthwash	Bacterial contamination in aerosol, cultured on MeReSa and Leeds Acinetobacter Agar plates at a distance of Two feet from the reference point to the patient's right. Two feet from behind the reference point. Two feet from the reference point to the patient's left. Three feet from the reference point to the patient's right. Three feet from the reference point to the patient's left. Five feet from the reference point to the patient's right. Five feet from the reference point to the patient's left.

						Nine feet from the reference point.
18	Sadun et al, ³⁷ 2020	Effectiveness of Pre- Procedural Rinsing with Essential Oils- Based Mouthrinse to Reduce Aerosol Contamination of Periodontitis Patients	Full mouth, double blind, RCT	30 patients 15 per group 2 groups	Test group: 20 mL of Test mouthwash (Listerine®) Control group: 20 mL of Placebo mouthwash (coloured distilled water)	Three different points specified as: 1 ft (30.48 cm), 2 ft (60.96 cm) and 3 ft (91.44 cm) from the scaling treatment site (patient's mouth) in Brain Heart Infusion (BHI) media plates in triplicate Petri dishes at the three designated positions.
19	Benna Paul et al, ³⁸ 2020	Effect of aloe vera as a preprocedural rinse in reducing aerosol contamination during ultrasonic scaling	Full mouth, RCT	60 patients 20 per group 3 groups	Group A (CHX): 0.2% chlorhexidine (CHX) (Rexidin®, Indoco Remedies Ltd., Aurangabad) Group B: (PVP-I): 1% PVP-I (Betadine®, Win-Medicare Pvt Ltd, New Delhi-PVP solution IP 10% W/V diluted to 1% using distilled water) Group C: (AV): 94.5% Aloe vera	Sheep blood agar plates, at two standardized locations-one at the patient's chest area and the other at operator's chest area.
20	Nisha et al, ³⁹ 2021	Comparison of chlorhexidine and hydrogen peroxide as preprocedural mouthrinse	Full mouth, RCT	90 patients 30 per group 3 groups	Group I: 0.12% chlorhexidine (CHX) Group II: 1.5%	Blood agar plates were placed at three different locations, i.e., patient's chest,

		during ultrasonic scaling: A triple-blinded randomized controlled clinical trial			hydrogen peroxide Group III: distilled water	operator's chest, and dental assistant's chest area
21	Swarga Jyothi das et al, ⁴⁰ 2022	Effects of preprocedural mouth rinse on microbial load in aerosols produced during the ultrasonic scaling: A randomized controlled trial.	Full mouth, RCT	80 patients, 20 per group 4 groups	Group A: no preprocedural mouth Rinse Group B: water Group C: chlorhexidine gluconate (0.2%) and Group D: herbal mouthwash	40 g of HIMEDIA Blood agar base in 1000 ml of distilled water, positioned at four different Position 1: Operatory room, 4 feet away from the dental chair (baseline count) Position 2: Chest of the patients during treatment Position 3: Chest of the operator during treatment Position 4: Chest of the assistant during treatment.
22	Chinnu Mary et al, ⁴¹ 2021	Self-Prepared Herbal Mouthwash Used as Pre-procedural Rinse in Reducing Dental Aerosol: A Substitute to Chemical Mouthrinse: A Clinico-Microbiological Study	Full mouth, double blind, RCT	20 patients, 5 per group 4 groups	Group A: neem Group B: 0.12% chlorhexidine Group C: triphala Group D (control): water	Chest, Spitoon from the reference point (i.e Patient's Mouth) on blood agar plates
23	Vyshanvi et al, ⁴² 2023	Efficacy of Oxygen-Enriched Mouthwash as a Pre-procedural	Full mouth, RCT	40 patients 20 per group 2 groups	Group 1 (test group) blue@m mouthwash Group 2: (control)	Blood agar plates were placed at the patient's chest and shoulder area

		Mouth Rinse Against Oral Microbes Produced During Ultrasonic Scaling.			group) chlorhexidine	
24	Sri vani et al, ⁴³ 2023	A Comparative Qualitative Analysis of Ozonised Water and Povidine Iodine as a Pre- Procedural Rinse in Chronic Periodontitis – A Randomized Controlled Clinical Trial.	Full mouth, double blind, RCT	30 patients 10 per group 3 groups	Group A: normal saline Group B: 5ml of 0.2 % PVP – I Group C: 4mg/l ozonised water	3 Reference points: the left side from the mouth at a distance of one feet, the right side from the mouth at a distance of one feet, and the area in front of the patient's foot at a distance of two feet. Fresh blood agar plates.
25	Yuti Malinda ⁴ 2024	Pre-procedural Mouth Rinses to Reduce Droplet Contamination During Ultrasonic Periodontal Scaling	Full mouth, RCT	28 patients 8 per group 4 groups	Group A: povidone-iodine mouthwash (Betadine®) Group B: 0.2% chlorhexidine digluconate (Minosep®) Group C: Essential oil (Listerine® Multiprotect Zero) Group D: aloe vera extract mouthwash (Aloclair® plus oral rinse mouthwash).	On the chest of the patient, the dentist, and the dental assistant in Nutrient agar plates

TABLE 1: Included studies for the review: Author, title, study design, type of intervention, microbial evaluation and aerosol collection.

S.no	Author	Duration of rinsing and scaling	outcome	Mean ± Standard deviation	Results	Conclusion
1	Fine et al, ²⁰ 1992	30 s preprocedural rinse followed by 10 mins of ultrasonic scaling	Bacterial count (CFU)	-----	Rinsing with the antiseptic mouthwash produced a 94.1% reduction in recoverable CFUs compared to the non-rinsed control, while the control rinse produced a 33.9% reduction. The difference between the mouthwash and control was statistically significant (P < .001).	Preprocedural rinsing with an antiseptic mouthwash can significantly reduce the microbial content of aerosols generated during ultrasonic scaling and may have potential in-office use as part of an infection control regimen.
2	Feres et al, ²¹ 2010	1 min preprocedural rinse followed by 10 mins of ultrasonic scaling	Bacterial count (CFU)	-----	CPC and CHX were equally effective in lowering the levels of spatter bacteria and performed better than water and no rinsing (P < .05, Kruskal-Wallis test). The composition of the spatter from the control groups showed higher proportions (P < .05, Kruskal-Wallis test) of Fusobacterium species and lower proportions of Capnocytophaga species when compared with the spatter from the CPC and CHX groups	A commercial mouthrinse containing 0.05% CPC when used as a preprocedural mouthrinse was equally effective as CHX in reducing the levels of spatter bacteria generated during ultrasonic scaling.

3	Devker et al, ²² 2012	2 mins preprocedural rinse followed by 10 mins of ultrasonic scaling	Bacterial count (CFU)	-----	<p>The enhanced efficacy of 0.2% chlorhexidine gluconate in reducing the CFUs. Comparison within groups showed that group II had significantly greater reduction in the level of aerosols as compared to group I ($p < 0.01$). Comparison within groups showed that group III was significantly more effective than groups I and II in reducing the level of aerosols ($p < 0.01$).</p> <p>The values obtained showed that all the three groups were effective in reducing the mean colony forming units (CFUs)</p>	Preprocedural rinse and high-volume suction were effective when used alone as well as together in reducing the microbial load of the aerosols produced during ultrasonic scaling.
4	Shanti Priya et al, ²³ 2012	1 minute of preprocedural rinse and ultrasonic scaling is done	Bacterial count (CFU)	Pre scaling CFU in Group II (Non-tempered CHX 0.2%) is 145.60 ± 19.68 . and with Group III (tempered CHX 0.2%) is 137.40 ± 16.99 .	The results showed that CFU in group III and group II were significantly reduced when compared to group I with $F=1084.92$, $P<0.001$ (ANOVA). Also, CFU in group III was significantly reduced when compared to group II with $P<0.001$.	When compared to sterile water, both were found superior, but Tempered chlorhexidine was more effective than non-tempered chlorhexidine.

				Post scaling CFU in Group II (Non-tempered CHX 0.2%) is 24.40±6.47. and with Group III (tempered CHX 0.2%) is 13.60±2.72.		
5	Serban et al, ²⁴ 2013	preprocedural rinse followed by ultrasonic scaling	Bacterial count (CFU)	Bacteria that grew on the plate was 118.01 +/- 25.07 CFU/m ³ and the mean number of hemolytic bacteria that grew on the plate was 10.68 +/- 4.75 CFU/m	Medium positive correlations were observed between decayed teeth and bacterial/hemolytic counts on dentist masks. Both bacterial and hemolytic counts were significantly lower in the chlorhexidine 0.1% rinse group compared to the sterile water group.	Simple measures, such as rinsing with 0.1% chlorhexidine mouthwash before treatment, reduce oral bacterial counts and thereby lower the number of aerosolized microbes.
6	Shetty et al, ²⁵ 2013	2 mins preprocedural rinse before scaling followed by 10 mins of ultrasonic scaling	Bacterial count (CFU)	-----	Comparison of mean CFUs of group 1 (control) with group 2 (chlorhexidine) showed a Z-value of 5.412 and p-value of <0.001 and 20.8006% difference which was found to be highly significant. Comparison of mean	Preprocedural dural rinsing with an effective antimicrobial mouthrinse during any dental treatment which generates aerosols, reduces the risk of cross contamination with infectious agents in

					<p>CFUs of group 1 (control) with group 3 (tea tree oil) showed a Z-value of 3.274 and p-value of <0.001 and 6.7257% difference which was found to be highly significant. Comparison of mean aerobic CFUs group 2 (chlorhexidine) with group 3 (tea tree oil) showed a Z-value of 5.387 and p-value of <0.001 and 27.7263% difference which was found to be highly significant.</p>	the dental operatory.
7	Kaur et al, ²⁶ 2014	1 min preprocedural rinse followed by 10 mins of ultrasonic scaling	Bacterial count (CFU)	Colony forming units according to different treatment and positions (anaerobic CFU) with CHX on chest is 281.55±199.4 and at 9 feet is 26±22.15. with PI on chest is 195.2±84.2 and 24.1±12.2 at 9 feet. with ozone irrigation is	High reduction of aerobic and anaerobic colony forming units (CFUs) in all three groups. In aerobic CFUs, CHX showed the highest reduction (57%) at mask position whereas at chest position and at 9 ft, PI showed higher CFU reductions (37% and 47%, respectively). In anaerobic CFUs, CHX showed the highest percentage of reduction at chest level (43%) and at 9 ft (44%).	CHX, PI and OZ showed similar effects in reducing aerobic and anaerobic CFU's at the chest mask and at 9 ft. OZ can be used as a preprocedural agent, considering its beneficial effects.

				<p>147.75±50.55 on chest and 28.8±13.65 at 9 feet.</p> <p>Under aerobic conditions, with CHX on chest is 120.55±85.7 and at 9 feet is 23.7±16.7.</p> <p>with PI on chest is 215.65±80.75 and 26.85±16.45 at 9 feet. With ozone irrigation is 120±59.2 on chest and 37.4±33.8 at 9 feet.</p>		
8	Gupta et al, ²⁷ 2014	1 min preprocedural rinse followed by 30 mins of ultrasonic scaling	Bacterial count (CFU)	-----	<p>CFUs in groups A and B were significantly reduced compared with group C, P <0.001 (analysis of variance). Also, CFUs in group A were significantly reduced compared with group B, P <0.05 (independent t-test). The numbers of CFUs were highest at the patient's chest</p>	<p>This study suggests that a routine preprocedural mouth rinse could eliminate the majority of bacterial aerosols generated by the use of an ultrasonic unit, and that 0.2% chlorhexidine gluconate is more effective than herbal mouthwash.</p>

					area and lowest at the assistant's chest area	
9	Swamina than et al, ²⁸ 2014	1 min preprocedural rinse followed by ultrasonic scaling	Bacterial count (CFU)	-----	Reduction in the bacterial load using 0.2% of chlorhexidine gluconate mouthwash is found to be significant in both saliva and aerosol produced du	Chlorhexidine mouthwash as a preprocedural rinse is more effective than the herbal mouthwash. Preprocedural rinse has a definite benefit in the treatment perspective but as aimed, the reduction in the bacterial load in saliva has not proportionately decrease the bacterial load in the aerosol.
10	Rekha et al, ²⁹ 2014	30 s preprocedural rinse followed by 30 mins of ultrasonic scaling	Bacterial count (CFU)	Mean colony forming units/agar plate (CFU/plate) according to treatment and locations during use of ultrasonic scaler on operator is 77.04±33.87 on patient is 27.08±12.31	The mean Colony Forming Units (CFUs) for control group was 114.50, Chlorhexidine group was 56.75 and herbal rinse group was 47.38.	Herbal rinse was found to be as effective as chlorhexidine in reducing splatter bacteria during ultrasonic scaling.
11	Sawhney et al, ³⁰ 2015	30 s preprocedural rinse followed by	Bacterial count (CFU)	-----	Out of all the three pre-procedural rinses 0.2% w/v Chlorhexidine is the	Use of pre-procedural rinses along with the use of high volume

		ultrasonic scaling			best in reducing aerobic bacteria (CFU) followed by Listerine and then Water.	suction apparatus significantly reduced the aerosol contamination
12	Saini et al, ³¹ 2015	60 s preprocedural rinse followed by 10 mins of ultrasonic scaling	Bacterial count (CFU)	CFUs (mean \pm SD) according to test group and location at P1 is 12.37 \pm 1.85, at P2 is 12.05 \pm 1.60, at P3 is 72.44 \pm 3.66, at P4 is 72.44 \pm 3.66, at P5 is 55.09 \pm 3.14 comparison of mean and SD values of CFUs in ClO ₂ is 11.24 \pm 1.41 and 0.2% CHX is 9.18 \pm 1.58	The results showed that CFUs in groups A and C were significantly reduced compared to group B, and P < 0.001 [analysis of variance (ANOVA)]. CFUs in group C underwent the highest reduction, but statistically there was no significant difference between the mean values of postprocedural CFUs in groups C and A (i.e., P > 0.05). The numbers of CFUs were the highest at the patient's chest area and lowest at the patient's front i.e., the 6 o'clock position.	This study proves that a regular preprocedural mouthrinse could significantly eliminate the majority of aerosols generated by the use of an ultrasonic unit, and that ClO ₂ mouthrinse was found to be statistically equally effective in reducing the aerosol contamination to 0.2% CHX gluconate.
13	Narayana et al, ³² 2016	30s of preprocedural rinse followed by 10 mins of ultrasonic scaling	Bacterial count (CFU)	Comparison of Colony forming units from bioaerosols between with pre-procedural rinse is 38.93 \pm 74.1 Comparison of Colony forming units from	Significant reduction in the CFUs when CHX (0.12%) preprocedural rinse (P < 0), or HVE (P < 0.001) or combination of both CHX (0.12%) and HVE were employed (P < 0.001). Maximum reduction in CFUs was observed when CHX (0.12%) and HVE	CHX (0.12%) and HVE were useful to reduce the dental bioaerosols; however, combination of both CHX (0.12%) and HVE is more efficient to reduce dental bioaerosols than individual method.

				<p>bioaerosols between with the use of high-volume evacuator is 13.13 ± 11.31</p> <p>Comparison of colony forming units from bioaerosols between with and without the use of high -volume evacuator and rinse is 41.36 ± 56.21.</p>	<p>were used in combination as compared to their individual use. A moderate significance was seen between A versus C groups but not with B versus C groups and A versus B groups.</p>	
14	Mohan et al, ³³ 2016	1 min preprocedural rinse followed by ultrasonic scaling	Bacterial count (CFU)	<p>Pre-procedural CFU with CHX is 667.9 ± 380.42.</p> <p>post-procedural CFU with chlorhexidine mouth wash is 222.7 ± 117.8.</p>	The results showed that CFUs decreased in patients who had a pre-rinse with chlorhexidine mouthwash when compared to patients with saline mouth rinse	Pre-procedural use of mouth rinse using chlorhexidine can significantly reduce the viable microbial content of dental aerosols and protect the operator from the bacterial hazards
15	Belén RETAM AL-VALDES et al, ³⁴ 2017	one minute with 20 ml of the solution followed by ultrasonic scaling	Bacterial count (CFU)	-----	When all locations were considered together, the aerosols from the CPC+Zn+F and CHX groups showed, respectively, 70% and 77% fewer CFUs than those from the	0.075% CPC, 0.28% zinc lactate and 0.05% sodium fluoride as a pre-procedural mouthwash was effective in reducing bacterial species

					<p>No Rinsing group and 61% and 70% than those from the Water group. The mean proportions of bacterial species from the orange complex were statistically significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower in aerosols from the CPC+Zn+F and CHX groups compared with the others two groups.</p>	<p>present in viable oral aerosols during prophylaxis with ultrasonic instruments.</p>
16	Joshi et al, ³⁵ 2017	1 min preprocedural rinse followed by 30 mins of ultrasonic scaling	Bacterial count (CFU)	-----	<p>Cetylpyridinium chloride (0.05%) as a pre-procedural rinse was found to be equally effective in reducing aerosol contamination when compared with 0.2% chlorhexidine rinse ($p > 0.05$). Also, greater reduction of CFU was found with the use of tempered rinses at 47°C with a highly statistically significant difference ($p < 0.001$).</p>	<p>pre-procedural rinse containing 0.05% cetylpyridinium chloride can be considered as a promising alternative in reducing aerosol contamination during ultrasonic scaling procedures when compared to the gold standard 0.2% chlorhexidine, with tempering the rinse showing the definite edge. Also, it can be concluded that the amount of viable bacteria in aerosol is maximum at the</p>

						<p>patient's chest area followed by the operator and assistant in a descending manner, thus reinforcing the use of personal protective barriers to minimize the risk to dental professionals.</p>
17	Rajachan drasekar an et al, ³⁶ 2019	30 s preprocedural rinse followed by 10 mins of ultrasonic scaling	Bacterial count (CFU)	-----	Herbal mouthwash (Himalaya Hiora Regular) showed a significant reduction in mean CFU of MRSA compared to 0.12% chlorhexidine. While herbal mouthwash was on par with 0.12% chlorhexidine in the reduction of A. baumannii	Both herbal mouthwash and chlorhexidine mouthwash was found to be effective against A. baumannii.
18	Sadun et al, ³⁷ 2020	1 min prior to dental scaling treatment procedure.	Bacterial count (CFU)	Reduction in microbial load between the test and control groups of periodontitis saliva samples is 61.79 ± 7.66 Test and control groups in bioaerosols from the periodontitis	Analysis done at three defined distance intervals from the operating site showed the level of bioaerosol contamination was highest at distance nearest to the treatment point of 1 ft. Based on counts of cfu, there was higher presence of microbial contaminant in bioaerosols of the control-rinsed group compared to the test-	Rinsing using Listerine® was effective towards reducing the microorganisms in saliva and oral cavity in general.

				<p>treatment group in control group is 1.32 ± 0.32 in test group is 0.18 ± 0.12</p> <p>Differences between test and control groups in bioaerosols from the periodontitis treatment group at three different distances using is 1.45 ± 0.47.</p>	<p>rinsed group using Listerine</p>	
19	Benna Paul et al, ³⁸ 2020	1 minute of preprocedural rinse and ultrasonic scaling is done after 20 mins.	Bacterial count (CFU)	<p>CFU after using chlorhexidine is 11.50 ± 1.51, for herbal mouthwash id 11.80 ± 2.17, aloe vera group is 12.65 ± 1.96.</p>	<p>There was statistically significant difference in the CFU counts between CHX group and PVP-I group and between AV group and PVP-I group. There was no difference between CHX group and AV group at both the locations.</p>	<p>94.5% AV as a preprocedural rinse is better than 1% PVP-I and comparable to 0.2% CHX in reducing CFU count.</p>
20	Nisha et al, ³⁹ 2021	1 minute of preprocedural rinse and ultrasonic scaling is done after 20 mins.	Bacterial count (CFU)	<p>Colony-forming units count in relation to Doctor's chest is 35.15 ± 2.64. Assistant's chest is 125.9 ± 4.76.</p>	<p>Least number of CFUs was found in the CHX group, followed by HP and DW groups. Location wise, the patient's chest area had the highest CFU count</p>	<p>Hydrogen peroxide had minimal side effects compared to CHX and could be used as an alternative to CHX as a preprocedural mouthrinse</p>

				Patient' chest is 16.12±1.84.	and the least was at the assistant's chest area. CFU count between the groups was statistically significant.	
21	Swarga Jyothi das et al, ⁴⁰ 2022	30 s preprocedural rinse followed by 30 mins of ultrasonic scaling	Bacterial count (CFU)	On the chest of patients with Chlorhexidine gluconate 70.55±31.78 and Herbal mouthwash is 129.70±53.35 . On chest of operator with Chlorhexidine gluconate 121.75±32.37 and Herbal mouthwash is 206.60±53.12 . On chest of assistant with Chlorhexidine gluconate 27.50±21.80 and	Microbial colonies were significantly reduced with chlorhexidine gluconate compared to that of others (P < 0.001), followed by herbal mouthwash and water. Again, microbial colonies were highest at the chest area of the operator and lowest at the chest area of the assistant.	Chlorhexidine gluconate (0.2%) is more effective in reducing the microbial load in aerosols produced during ultrasonic scaling compared to that of herbal mouthwash and water when used as a preprocedural mouth rinse.

				Herbal mouthwash is 79.00±47.60. Microbial colonies involving all the groups at various positions and pairwise comparison with chlorhexidine gluconate is 73.26±28.65 Herbal 138.43±51.35 .		
22	Chinnu Mary et al, ⁴¹ 2021	30 s preprocedural rinse followed by 10 mins of ultrasonic scaling	Bacterial count (CFU)	Bioaerosol production by counting colony forming units in spittoon, chest and tray is 36.13±37.52, 83±27.55, 19.66±22.93.	The study suggests that 10 ml of Neem Mouth rinse when used 10 minutes prior to ultrasonic scaling is more potent in reducing the aerosol contamination as compared to the Triphala mouth rinse and commercially available 0.2 % Chlorhexidine mouthrinse.	10 ml of Neem Mouth rinse when used 10 minutes prior to ultrasonic scaling is more potent in reducing the aerosol contamination as compared to the Triphala mouth rinse and commercially available 0.2 % Chlorhexidine mouthrinse. Neem> Chlorhexidine >Triphala> Water

23	Vyshanvi et al, ⁴² 2023	60 s preprocedural rinse followed by 15-20 mins of ultrasonic scaling	Bacterial count (CFU)	<p>Post treatment bacterial load in the experimental group on chest of the patient is 59.8 ± 2.5 and shoulder of the patient is 35.3 ± 3.6.</p> <p>Post-treatment bacterial load in the control group on the chest of the patient is 104.8 ± 3.2 and on the shoulder of the patient is 75.3 ± 2.8.</p>	<p>The mean initial bacterial load after the use of water (placebo) as pre-rinse on the patients' chest area (122.4 ± 0.6) and shoulder area (109.3 ± 2.6) in the experimental group was similar to the bacterial load seen on the chest area (126.2 ± 4.8) and shoulder area (115.4 ± 3.8) in the control group. The CFUs found in blood agar plates placed on the chest (59.8 ± 2.5) and shoulder (35.3 ± 3.6) areas of patients in group 1 were less as compared to CFUs found in blood agar plates placed on the chest (104.8 ± 3.2) and shoulder (75.3 ± 2.8) areas of patients in group 2. The difference between both groups was statistically significant with a p-value of ≤ 0.05.</p>	<p>Reduction in the bacterial load in the aerosols that are emitted during the ultrasonic scaling procedure with the use of oxygen-enriched mouthwash (blue®m) as a preprocedural rinse when compared with chlorhexidine</p>
24	Sri vani et al, ⁴³ 2023	60 s preprocedural rinse followed by 15 mins of	Bacterial count (CFU)	Intra group comparison (ozone group) ,0.2% povidine	The results showed high percentage reduction of aerobic colony forming	Ozone therapy is quite predictable and conservative.

		ultrasonic scaling		iodine group and control group) is 43.43±16.38, 66.96±35.32. Intragroup comparison on right side, left side and front side is 35.3±17.74, 84.75±36.06 and 45.55±23.97.	units (CFUs) in all three groups. In aerobic culturing, OZ showed the highest reduction in all three positions.	
25	Yuti Malinda ⁴ ⁴ 2024	30 s preprocedural rinse followed by ultrasonic scaling	Bacterial count (CFU)	Reduction of CFU on patients is 16.74±26.80. Reduction of CFU in dentist is 10.71±17.60. Reduction of CFU on assistant is 5.35±13.82.	The mouthwash does not have any impact on the variable reduction CFU in Patient-Dentist-Dental Assistant. However, the data clearly indicates that all mouthwashes effectively decrease the number of colonies.	The reduction in CFU after rinse with mouthwash highlights the significance of preprocedural mouthwash in lowering oral bacteria numbers prior to minimizing bacteria in dental aerosol formation.

TABLE 2: Included studies for the review: Author, duration of scaling and rinsing, study outcome, results and conclusion

Study Limitations and Future research directions: There are certain limitations to this review. Our review focused exclusively on ultrasonic scaling procedures, highlighting the need for further research to determine the optimal mouthrinses for pre-rinsing in COVID-19-affected patients and periodontal procedures. The results of our review should be interpreted with caution, as the primary outcome (reduction in aerosolized microorganisms) is a surrogate marker for occupational infection among dental personnel or patients. While pre-procedural mouthrinses significantly reduce microorganisms in dental procedure-generated aerosols, the impact of this reduction on infection rates remains unknown. Wide variation in rinse concentration, volume, temperature (tempered vs. non-tempered), and contact time; inconsistent use of adjunctive measures (high-volume evacuation, assistant suction, ventilation), and differences in scaler power/water flow was not highlighted. baseline microbial loads, environmental conditions (room size/air exchanges), adherence to rinse

protocols, coolant composition/temperature, and adverse effects (e.g., CHX staining, taste disturbance) were inconsistently reported. Currently, there is no direct evidence demonstrating that pre-procedural mouthrinse decreases the rate of clinical infection in dental offices, emphasizing the need for further investigation.

Future research should involve well-powered, standardized randomized controlled trials with uniform protocols for mouthrinse use and aerosol assessment. Studies incorporating pathogen-specific detection methods and evaluating the combined effect of mouthrinses with other aerosol-reduction strategies are needed to strengthen evidence and guide clinical infection control practices.

Conclusion: A pre-procedural mouthrinse is a simple yet powerful tool in infection control, reducing microbial load and enhancing the safety of clinical procedures. Incorporating this practice into routine dental and medical care can contribute significantly to overall patient and provider protection. Our systematic review and meta-analysis revealed that pre-procedural rinsing remains a crucial component of periodontal prophylaxis, particularly in dental clinics. The findings suggest that rinsing with selected antimicrobial solutions (excluding saline or water) for 30 seconds to 2 minutes effectively reduces aerosol contamination during periodontal prophylaxis. Incorporating pre-procedural rinsing into dental practice can have mutual benefits for both operators and patients by minimizing bacterial exposure. This highlights the importance of adopting pre-procedural rinsing as a standard protocol in dental clinics to enhance infection control and ensure a safer environment.

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